

Corporate Governance Sustainability Regulation: The Impact of Sustainability Competencies on ESG Ratings - An Exploratory Study of European and Japanese Banks

Silke Waterstraat¹[0000-0002-8279-7089]

¹ University of Applied Sciences Northwestern Switzerland, Basel, Switzerland
silke.waterstraat@fhnw.ch

Abstract. Global lawmakers and standard setters, e.g., the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) as well as many other countries in the world, such as Europe and Japan are continuously shaping their regulatory frameworks in the area sustainability with a strong focus on environmental disclosures and with corporate governance being a rather deprioritized area. This study examines if the number of board directors with sustainability expertise and sustainability leadership has a positive effect on the ESG ratings of EURO STOXX Banks and Japanese TOPIX Banks. Results indicate that sustainability expertise on boards of European and Japanese banks is still rather low, but that sustainability leadership with Japanese banks is relatively high. Nevertheless, ESG ratings of Japanese banks are rather low and much lower than those of their European peers.

Keywords: Sustainability regulation, Corporate Governance, Europe, Japan, Banks.

1 Introduction

The European Commission approved the European Green Deal in 2019 to achieve climate-neutrality for Europe by 2050 [1]. Since then, it adopted a set of regulations, including the EU taxonomy, which entered into force on 12 July 2020 [2]. The current environmental taxonomy has been considered a starting point for a succeeding social and governance taxonomy according to the European Commission [3]. The further development and a approval of a social taxonomy has been put on hold since then due to diverging political views; despite intensive consultations and the findings and appeals of researchers and practitioners emphasizing the necessity of a holistic regulatory framework for sustainability including the social and governance dimension [4,5,6,7]. The development of a governance taxonomy occurs even slower: While the European Commission opened a consultation in late 2020 [1] on the realignment of corporate governance with key aspects of a sustainable economy, a full, separate governance taxonomy report or draft has not been proposed so far but has been included as a rather small part in the report on the social taxonomy [3]. The latter aim to increase corporate governance in firms, amongst others elaborates on “traditional governance factors” [3, p.61], “addressing purely economic issues” [3, p.61], e.g., “ownership and

Smuts, Hanlie & Hinkelmann, Knut (2024). Proceedings of the 4th Conference Society 5.0 - Innovation for Sustainable and Inclusive Social Good, Volume 2, Mauritius, 26-28 June 2024, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11612759

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11661083

shareholders' rights; the composition, development and evaluation of boards; financial reporting and disclosure; qualifications and conflicts of interest of board members; audits; risk management; remuneration; and legal-compliance systems" [3, p.61]. In many countries corporate governance have been taken place [10] since two decades motivated by "a desire for more transparency and accountability [...] to increase investor confidence" [9].

Japan's corporate governance system has been in the spotlight, with the re-vitalization of its stock market presumably driven by corporate governance reforms [11]. Japan has started to reform its traditional corporate governance system following the bursting of the stock market bubble at the end of the 1980s [8]. The reforms are usually divided into two phases [8]: "First, the period from the early 1990s to the end of 2011, a point in time that in some ways marks the end of the great financial crisis of 2008/9, and second, the period from the time the Abe government took office in 2012" [8, p.93]. The corporate governance code from February 2015 [12] marks the starting point for significant changes in the second phase of reforms. Main goal was to strengthen the weight and influence of independent directors [12]. In 2015, corporate law was changed to allow organizational forms of companies segregating management and supervisory boards [12]. In 2021, for companies listed on the Prime Market of the Tokyo Stock Exchange further regulations were strengthened [8,13]: At least one-third of the directors must be independent outside directors [8], "or the majority if the company has a majority shareholder" [8, p.100]. Also, regulations for other market segments were put in place [8,13]. And companies must explain and disclose the reason and objective of shareholdings in other companies [8,14]. As in many other countries the governance codes are not mandatory [10], but Japan follows the apply or explain approach [14]. In 2022 and 2023 the Tokyo Stock Exchange (TSE) further increased pressure on companies not managing towards increasing "corporate value" [15] and "implementing management that is conscious of cost of capital and stock price" [16]. Further, the TSE requires from non-compliant companies to disclose action plans to increase their price to book ratios to above 1 [16]. This is not the end of regulatory activity, according to CNBC (2024), "the Japanese government and the TSE have plans in the works for increasing corporate board independence and female representation" [17].

Global lawmakers and standard setters, e.g., the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) as well as many other countries in the world, such as Europe and Japan are continuously shaping their regulatory frameworks in the area sustainability with a strong focus on environmental disclosures [2,18] with corporate governance being rather a rather deprioritized area of sustainability regulation. Japan's corporate governance reform discussion, still rather focusing on traditional corporate governance factors, might benefit from the initial European discussion on governance factors directly linked to sustainability matters [3] in the EU taxonomy as well as in the Gender Balance Directive [27] and CSDDD [29], in particular in the areas of sustainability competencies in the highest governance body, transparency on sustainability targets and the incentives to achieve these targets as well as criteria on sustainability-linked pay and diversity [3]. This study will focus on sustainability competencies, potentially not only adding to the discussion in Japan, but also to Europe's halt on the discussions [4,5] could be revitalized by a data-driven regulatory impact study.

2 Theoretical Background, Literature Review and Hypotheses

2.1 Theoretical Background and Literature Review

According to the World Economic Forum (2023), 98% of CEOs worldwide consider it as their job to make their businesses more sustainable, but “many are concerned it could hurt their bottom line” [19] but consider it as “more complex and costly [...] to sticking to business as usual” [19]. This view is supported by the United Nations Global Compact initiative highlighting that it “is now firmly acknowledged by researchers, investors and executives that corporate sustainability is key to long-term profitability and viability of most, if not all, companies” [20, p.4]. However, some studies find that board directors think too much time is spent on sustainability [30], see little financial impact on the business [32] or feel “ill-equipped” in ESG [31]. Most recently, an analysis from Copenhagen Business School and Competent Boards (2024) found that board’s sustainability competency has room for improvement as stated by 84% of public companies in Europe and 76% in the United States respectively [33]. In Japan, ESG competence greenwashing risks up to board level are discussed with regulators and in the press [34]. Also, sustainability expertise on boards is still rather low [1,35]: “Currently, less than one percent (0.8%) of 110,000 directors across 7,226 public companies globally have a professional background in sustainability” [36].

The composition of the highest governance body, e.g., the board, is considered along with other factors (e.g., alignment of interests of the company with directors’ duties, focus to the long-term, board remuneration) key to promote sustainable business management [21,22,23]. For similar and additional sustainability related governance factors taken up or being discussed on EU level, e.g., transparency on sustainability targets [24], incentivization [21,22,25,26] as well as sustainability linked board remuneration [21,26] and diversity [43] supportive empirical research could be found.

The resource dependency theory, human capital theory, agency theory and social psychological theory [37,38] provide theoretical background why sustainability competencies on boards help to make companies more sustainable [38]. “These theories aim to explain how external resources of the organization (resource dependency theory [39]), e.g., the board of directors, and their education and experiences (human capital theory [41]), their degree of independence (agency theory [40]) and diversity (social psychological theory [42]) may influence the behavior and performance of the organization” [38, p.130]. So, “the absence of relevant knowledge and expertise inside the board might significantly undermine a board’s capacity to identify and discuss sustainability risks and impacts” [1, p.3, 38].

Research on the relationship between board characteristics and the ESG performance of firms most widely uses parameters such as the share of independent directors [43,44,54,55], (gender) diversity [43,44,54,55], (national) diversity [43], board size [43,44,54,55] and the existence of a sustainability committee [43,44,55]. The independence of board members is considered advantageous to promote sustainable business strategies [45,46,47,54,55] by some researchers, while others found contrary results [44,43]. Diversity is a multi-faceted concept encompassing age [55], gender, nationality, race [1] as well as “different backgrounds and experiences – including sustainability

expertise” [38, p.130], positively impacting not only corporate sustainability, but also economic [48] and other extra-financial areas [22,23]. Some studies with a focus on gender representation found a positive impact of female board participation on ESG performance [47,49,54,55] or financial performance [50,47,51], whereas others could not show an impact on financial performance [37,52,53]. Regarding board size, most studies find a positive impact on ESG performance [43,44,55], only one a negative [54]. The impact of sustainability committees on ESG ratings was examined in the Gulf region [49], for Italian banks [55] and for European banks [44] showing a positive influence.

As the banking sector has – through its financial intermediary function [38] – a key function for the transition to a more sustainable economy [44], further studies on the impact of board characteristics on ESG performance were conducted with a focus on the banking sector [37,38]. However, sustainability competencies have only been studied in one exploratory study for European banks in 2021, with no significant results of the impact of sustainability expertise on ESG performance, but of sustainability leadership on Chairperson- or CEO-level [37]. However, since then, regulatory activity in the area of sustainability significantly increased in Europe putting pressure on businesses and potentially boards to increase sustainability expertise. Also the Japanese regulatory activities significantly increased. The impact of board characteristics on ESG ratings has neither been studied for Japan nor for specifically banks in Japan. Studies published so far on Japanese firms showed the impact of board characteristics (e.g., board size, independence, diversity) on environmental performance [56], the influence of top management’s personal values [57] or board compensation [58] on ESG performance.

Therefore, this study focuses on the impact of sustainability competencies on boards on the ESG ratings of European and Japanese banks. Results might contribute to the regulatory discussion on fostering sustainability in both Japan and Europe.

2.2 Hypotheses

The given theoretical framework on the resource dependence theory and human capital theory, regulatory requirements and academic research on board characteristics [38,49] provide the theoretical basis why sustainability expertise could influence ESG ratings and a more sustainability oriented way of doing business. Theory and empirical studies [38,49] suggest a positive relationship between sustainability competencies on board level and ESG performance.

To test whether a revitalization in Europe or a consideration in Japan of regulatory discussion and action for sustainability competencies on boards would make sense and impact sustainable business management in firms, the following main hypothesis has been formulated:

Hypothesis 1: The number of board directors with sustainability expertise has a positive effect on the ESG ratings of EURO STOXX Banks 30 and TOPIX 17 BANKS.

The second hypothesis takes account of the fact that previous studies found a positive influence of the CEO or the Chairperson on ESG performance in both Europe and Japan

[37,38,57]. Following Alm and Winberg (2016) who studied the impact of female leadership on firms' financial performance, sustainability leadership will be measured with either the Chairperson or the CEO having a sustainability-oriented profile on the firm's website.

Hypothesis 2: Sustainability leadership has a positive effect on the ESG ratings of EURO STOXX Banks 30 and TOPIX 17 BANKS.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Data

In line with recent studies [30,37,54], data on ESG ratings, board of directors' characteristics and further financial data has been collected from Thomson Reuter's DataStream (now acquired by the London Stock Exchange Group) and was complemented for board of directors' characteristics manually from respective corporate websites [37]. Data includes 27 major European banks from the EURO STOXX Banks 30 index and 78 Japanese banks from the TOPIX Banks Index. Following recent studies [37,38,44,47] an 8-year panel dataset (from 2015-2022) has been constructed. The overall sample consists of 4446 director-firm-year observations, after deletion for missing values. Based on recent studies [37,38,54,55], the dependent variable to test the hypotheses represents the ESG performance rating from Thomson Reuters.

The independent variables of primary interest are sustainability expertise on board level (SUSTEXP) and sustainability leadership (SUSTLEAD) and their impact on ESG ratings of European and Japanese banks. Previous research [37,38,44,54] used different control variables, e.g., the share of women on the board of directors (WBOD), the number of foreigners on the board (FORBOD), the age of board members (AGEBOD), the share of independent directors (BODIND), board size (BODS) and the existence of a sustainability committee (SUSTCO). Following previous studies [37,38,54], further control variables are added, which might impact the ESG performance: Bank size (BANKSI), return on equity (ROE), leverage (LEV) and country-specific variables measured by the GDP [37,38,54,59] (see table 1).

Table 1. Measurement of independent / control variables [38, adapted from Waterstraat et al. (2021)]

Independent Variable	Measurement	Exp. Relationship with ESG Rating	Sources
SUSTEXP	Proportion of directors with sustainability expertise divided by the total number of directors on the board	Positive	Ceres (2015)
SUSTLEAD	Dummy variable that is equal to 1 if the bank has a Chairperson or CEO with sustainability profile, 0 otherwise	Positive	Nguyen (2024), Waterstraat et al. (2021), Alm & Winberg (2016)
WBOD	Total number of women on the board of directors divided by the total number of board members	Positive	Miranda et al. (2023), Menicucci et al. (2022), Konstantin & Elena (2022), Arayassi et al. (2020), Rao et al. (2017)

FORBOD	Total number of foreigners on the board of directors divided by the total number of board members	Positive	Konstantin & Elena (2022)
AGEBOD	Average age of board members	None	Menicucci et al. (2022),
BODIND	Percentage of independent board members divided by the total number of board members	Positive / negative	Miranda et al. (2023), Menicucci et al. (2022), Konstantin & Elena (2022), Arayassi et al. (2020), Garas et al. (2017)
BODS	Number of board members	Positive / negative	Miranda et al. (2023), Menicucci et al. (2022), Konstantin & Elena (2022), Birindelli et al. (2018)
SUSTCO	Dummy variable that is equal to 1 if the bank has a sustainability committee, 0 otherwise	Positive	Konstantin & Elena (2022), Birindelli et al. (2018)
BANKSI	Total assets (Euro) of the bank	Positive	Tamini et al (2017), Carter et al. (2010)
ROE	Bank's net income divided by the value of its total shareholders' equity	Positive / negative	Setó-Pamies (2015)
LEV	Tier 1 Capital as percentage of total assets (proxy for the Basel 3 leverage ratio). For European banks only, as Japanese banks do not report this ratio.	Positive	Helfaya and Moussa (2017)
GDP	Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita based on purchasing power parity (PPP)	Positive / negative	Fernandez-Feijoo et al. (2014)

3.2 Methodology

In line with the methodology approach of previous studies [37,38,47], the effect of the independent variables on the ESG rating has been tested through panel data analysis to control for omitted and / or unobserved variables. Therefore, a fixed effects (with respect to random effects) model was chosen, as it can also partly mitigate endogeneity issues [37,38,64]. “Natural logarithmic transformations of the numerical (non-index) variables of the age of board members, board size, GDP and bank size have been performed to better approximate a normal distribution and overcome a possible problem of heteroskedasticity” [37,38, p.146]. In line with previous studies [37,38], the OLS fixed effects regression model is estimated as:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}, t=1,2,3,4,5 \quad (1)$$

“where y is the dependent variable, the ESG rating, β_0 is the constant, the variable X , e.g., the variables of interest, are the different board characteristics as per table 1, ε is independent disturbance, i stands for the individual bank, and t stands for the years covered by the data sample” [38, p. 146]. “Following previous research [37,38,51,61] the OLS fixed effects regression model is complemented by a Hausman’s specification test to test whether X is a truly endogenous variable [37]. The respective 2SLS regression model is estimated as follows” [38, p. 146]:

$$x = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 A + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

“where x is the dependent variable, the ESG rating, α_0 is the constant, the variable A , the different board characteristics as per table 1, ε is independent disturbance, i stands for the individual bank, and t stands for the year covered by the data sample” [38, p. 146].

4 Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 and 3 show the descriptive statistics for the dependent and independent variables for European and Japanese Banks. The descriptive statistics include the mean, standard deviation, the minimum and the maximum.

The mean of ESG ratings of European banks is 64% and for Japanese Banks 36%. The average ESG score is in line with previous research [37,38] for European Banks. Sustainability expertise on boards shows a mean of 21% in European and 27% in Japanese banks, respectively. Sustainability leadership, e.g., a CEO or Chairperson with sustainability experience, exists with a rather low number of 16% of the European companies in average, but 39% with the Japanese banks. The share of woman on boards and the share of foreigners on boards stand at 16% and 0.4% for Japanese banks, and at 35% and 7% in the case of European banks. The share of woman on boards in European banks remains rather low but seemed to increase compared to previous research findings [37,38], while being even lower in Japanese banks. The average age is 59 years on the board of a European bank and 65 years on the board of a Japanese bank. The proportion of independent directors on boards is 67% for European and is in line with previous research [37,38] and similar for Japanese banks with 69%. In average, 31% of the European banks have a sustainability committee on board level, with 8% of the Japanese banks.

Table 2. European Banks: Descriptive statistics for the dependent and independent variables

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
ESG Rating	0.64	0.14	0.29	0.87
Sustainability expertise	0.21	0.23	0	1
Sustainability leadership	0.16	0.37	0	1
Women on the board of directors	0.35	0.13	0	0.78
Foreigners on the board of directors	0.07	0.09	0	0.5
Age of the board of directors	58.92	3.1	52.5	66.3
Board independence	0.66	0.24	0	1
Board size	14.19	4.14	6	25
Sustainability Committee	0.31	0.46	0	1
Bank size	5.895	1.15	2.9	7.89
Return on equity	2.01	0.89	-3.91	4.67
Leverage	1.77	0.33	0.47	2.58
GDP per capita, PPP	10.47	0.3	10.05	11.49

FORBOD	.340**	.157*	.288**	1										
AGEBOD	.160	.417**	.396**	.320**	1									
BODIND	.176*	.118	.232**	.295**	.067	1								
BODS	-.174**	-.092	-.104	-.272**	-.207*	-.541**	1							
SUSTCO	.468**	.197*	.235**	.259**	.320**	.010	.015	1						
BANKSI	.162*	-.087	.153*	.340**	.187*	-.326**	.377**	.178*	1					
ROE	-.021	-.106	-.049	-.031	-.107	.067	-.271**	-.111	-.228*	1				
LEV	.255*	.018	-.142	-.135	.112	-.141	-.047	-.111	-.397**	.087	1			
GDP	-.015	.012	.066	.197**	.190	.210*	-.009	.027	.034	.008	-.047	1		

[*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1]

Table 5. Japanese Banks: Correlation matrix

Variable	SUSTEXP	SUSTLEAD	WBOD	FORBOD	AGEBOD	BODIND	BODS	SUSTCO	BANKSI	ROE	GDP
SUSTEXP	1										
SUSTLEAD	.575**	1									
WBOD	.022	-.268**	1								
FORBOD	-.038	-.089	.10	1							
AGEBOD	.166	.231*	.112	.032	1						
BODIND	-.066	-.326**	.338**	.021	.331**	1					
BODS	-.352*	.134	-.207*	.151	-.168	-.241*	1				
SUSTCO	-.131	-.135	.152	.597**	-.030	.132	.323**	1			
BANKSI	-.358**	-.359**	.063	.206*	.182	-.012	.497**	.267*	1		
ROE	-.097	-.090	-.032	.134	-.109	.258*	-.027	.078	-.236*	1	
GDP	.016	0.26	-.439**	-.265**	-.097	-.052	.078	-.220	.011	-.026	1

[*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1]

The result of the fixed effects regression is presented in table 6. The results show that none of the independent variables of primary interest is statistically significant for European banks. This is contrary to a study in 2020, where a significant positive relationship between sustainability lead and ESG rating could be found [38]. Comparably to the study in 2020, a significant negative relationship between the board size and the ESG rating is shown [38], while in other previous research, a positive relation between board size and ESG performance was found [37].

Table 6. European Banks: Fixed effects regression results

Variable	Regression Coefficient	Robust Standard Error
SUSTEXP	.061	.072
SUSTLEAD	.008	.047
WBOD	.060	.156
FORBOD	-.140	.182
AGEBOD	.408	.367
BODIND	-.066	.074

BODS	-0.111*	.063
SUSTCO	.046	.033
BANKSI	-.008	.018
ROE	-.010	.013
LEV	.047	.045
GDP	-.052	.045
Constant	-.200	1.703
R-squared	.206	.122
Regression Model	0.454*	1.727

[*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1]

In the case of Japanese banks, there are significant negative relationships between sustainability lead (10% significance level), board independence (5% significance level) and ESG performance and significant positive relationships between age and board size and ESG performance.

Table 7. Japanese Banks: Fixed effects regression results

Variable	Regression Coefficient	Robust Standard Error
SUSTEXP	.036	.048
SUSTLEAD	-.123*	.068
WBOD	-.013	.260
FORBOD	1.184	1.082
AGEBOD	1.758**	.564
BODIND	-.382**	.176
BODS	.159*	.085
SUSTCO	-.104	.161
BANKSI	-.015	.016
ROE	.206***	.048
GDP	-.180	.221
Constant	-5.286	3.246
R-squared	.434	.139
Regression Model	0.752***	3.559

[*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1]

The result of the Hausman's specification test results in an R^2 of .2161 for Japanese banks, with regression coefficients for SUSTEXP and SUSTLEAD of .023 (standard error .054) and -.134 (standard error .077) with statistical significance at the 5% level for the latter. Further, it shows an R^2 of .0574, with regression coefficients for

SUSTEXP and SUSTLEAD of .090 (standard error .044) and .0719 (standard error .028) with statistical significance both at the 5% level for European Banks.

5 Conclusion

For the European banks, the fixed regression model resulted in no, but the Hausman's specification test in a significant relationship between the primary independent variables sustainability expertise and sustainability leadership with the ESG rating. For Japanese banks, the fixed regression shows and the Hausman's specification tests show a negative significant relationship between sustainability leadership on boards and the ESG ratings from Thomson Reuters Datastream.

In summary, data based on the indices EURSTOXX 30 Banks, Topix 17 Banks as well as Thomson Reuters Datastream show mixed results. While European data revealed either no relationships or results supporting the hypothesis that sustainability expertise and sustainability leadership positively impact the ESG rating of the banks, e.g., contradictory results, the results for Japan were rather surprising. The negative relationship between ESG ratings and sustainability leadership might be driven by still rather overall low ESG ratings in Japanese banks, which might be driven by other factors, e.g., lack of coverage, English reporting information and time invested by international ESG rating agencies. The fact that sustainability leadership does not have a positive impact on ESG ratings with the European Banks contradicts previous results [38] is surprising in the context of increased regulatory activity, which might imply an increase in sustainability experienced leadership profiles. However, potentially, the focus is set on other competencies, which can be also observed in the means in Europe versus Japan, with 39% of the banks having sustainability leadership with only 16% in Europe. It is also interesting to see that sustainability expertise on boards is in average higher for Japanese banks than for European banks.

The study might conclude that there is no impact of sustainability expertise on boards on ESG performance of firms. However, further studies could consider including additional ESG rating data providers, such as Morningstar (Sustainalytics), Bloomberg, S&P given the known different ESG rating methodologies applied by the before-mentioned agencies. Also, the data is still limited to a small number of banks in Europe and Japan: The company sample might be expanded to additional banks in Europe and Japan or all stock market listed companies to get additional insights. Potentially, additional and more specific measures of sustainability could be used dependent variable. Also, policymakers can draw insightful lessons learnt from the descriptive statistics found by this study. The fact that Japanese banks show higher means in terms of sustainability leadership and sustainability expertise on their boards might be a useful information for further discussions. In Japan, the rather low ESG ratings could be a source for discussion in the context of the before mentioned initiatives of the TSE and the overall reform process on corporate governance in Japan. In line with some studies, the research could be enhanced by the impact not only on ESG ratings, but also on stock market and financial performance [37] to gain further understanding on potential regulatory measures.

References

1. European Commission, EY: Study on directors' duties and sustainable corporate governance. Internet (2020): <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/e47928a2-d20b-11ea-adf7-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>, last accessed 2024/03/24.
2. European Commission: EU taxonomy for sustainable activities. Internet: EU taxonomy for sustainable activities - European Commission (europa.eu) (2024), last accessed 2024/03/24.
3. European Commission – Platform on Sustainable Finance: Final Report on Social Taxonomy (February 2022). Internet: Platform on Sustainable Finance's report on social taxonomy | European Commission (europa.eu), last accessed 2024/03/24.
4. Zetsche, D.A., Bodellini, M., Consiglio, R.: The EU Sustainable Finance Framework in Light of International Standards. *Journal of International Economic Law*, Volume 25, Issue 4, December 2022, 659–679, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jiel/jgac043>.
5. Cleary Gottlieb Steen & Hamilton: A Social and Governance Taxonomy for Europe: Extending the EU ESG Framework to Socially Sustainable Activities and Sustainable Governance (2022). Internet: [a-social-taxonomy-for-europe-extending-the-eu-esg-framework-to-socially-sustainable-activities-and-companies-corporate-governance.pdf](https://www.clearygottlieb.com/~/media/ClearyGottliebSteenHamilton/~/media/Default.aspx?g=82411e50-0f15-4f2e-ab4b-43050b113120) (clearygottlieb.com) (2022), last accessed 2024/03/24.
6. Leitão, M., Teles, G., da Silva, S.: ESG: What About The S and the G? (2023). Internet: <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=82411e50-0f15-4f2e-ab4b-43050b113120>, last accessed 2024/03/24.
7. Ainger, J., Arons, S.: EU Puts Key Plank of ESG Rulebook on Hold Amid Infighting (2022). Internet: <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2022-07-31/europe-to-put-key-plank-of-esg-rulebook-on-hold-amid-infighting?leadSource=verify%20wall>, last accessed 2024/03/24.
8. Kustner, C., Waterstraat, S.: Corporate Governance and Corporate Performance: Case Study Japan. In: Hüttche, T. (eds) *Finance in Crises* (2023). Contributions to Finance and Accounting. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48071-3_7.
9. Mallin, C.A.: *Corporate Governance* (2016, 5th Edition). Oxford University Press. Oxford.
10. ECGI – European Corporate Governance Institute: Codes (2024). Internet: <https://www.ecgi.global/content/codes?page=1>, last accessed 2024/04/04.
11. Reuters (Yamazaki, M., Wee, R.): After Nikkei's record run, investors want to know if Japan has changed for real (Reuters, 28 February 2024). Internet: <https://www.reuters.com/markets/asia/after-nikkeis-record-run-investors-want-know-if-japan-has-changed-real-2024-02-28/>, last accessed 2024/04/04.
12. Goto, G., Matsunaka, M., & Kozuka, S.: Japan's gradual reception of independent directors: An empirical and political-economic analysis (2017). In: D. W. Puchniak, H. Baum, & L. Nottage (Eds.), *Independent directors in Asia* (p. 135–175). Cambridge University Press.
13. Tokyo Stock Exchange, Inc.: Japan's Corporate Governance Code – Seeking sustainable corporate growth and increased corporate value over the mid- to long-term (2021). Internet: https://www.jpx.co.jp/english/news/1020/b5b4pj000000jvvr-att/20180602_en.pdf, last accessed 2024/04/04.
14. Milhaupt, C. Evaluating Abe's third arrow: How significant are Japan's recent corporate governance reforms? (2017, October 31). Columbia Law and Economics Working Paper No. 561. Internet: Retrieved May 25, 2023, from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2925497>, last accessed 2024/04/04.
15. Tokyo Stock Exchange, Inc.: Market restructuring (2022). Internet: <https://www.jpx.co.jp/english/equities/improvements/market-structure/01.html>, last accessed 2024/04/04.

16. Tokyo Stock Exchange, Inc.: Action on Cost of Capital-Conscious Management and Other Requests (2023). Internet: <https://www.jpx.co.jp/english/news/1020/e20230414-01.html>, last accessed 2024/04/04.
17. CNBC (Tan, C.): Japan wants higher returns for investors — here's what it's doing (2024). Internet: <https://www.cnbc.com/2024/01/12/japan-wants-higher-returns-for-investors-heres-what-its-doing.html>, last accessed 2024/04/04.
18. IFRS: General Sustainability-related Disclosures (2023). Internet: <https://www.ifrs.org/projects/completed-projects/2023/general-sustainability-related-disclosures/>, last accessed 2024/04/04.
19. World Economic Forum: Profit vs sustainability: Reconciling the sustainable transformation myth (2023). Internet: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2023/06/the-myth-of-profit-vs-sustainability-reconciling-sustainable-transformation/>, last accessed 2024/04/04.
20. United Nations Global Compact: A New Agenda for the Board of Directors: Adoption and Oversight of Corporate Sustainability. <https://www.unglobalcompact.org/library/303> (2012), last accessed 2021/02/24.
21. European Commission, EY: Study on directors' duties and sustainable corporate governance. Internet: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/e47928a2-d20b-11ea-adf7-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> (2020), last accessed 2024/04/04.
22. Ferrero Ferrero, I., Fernández Izquierdo, M.Á., Muñoz Torres, M.J.: Integrating Sustainability into Corporate Governance: An Empirical Study on Board Diversity. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 22(4), 193-207 (2015).
23. Zang, J.Q., Zhu, H., Ding, H.: Board Composition and Corporate Social Responsibility: An Empirical Investigation in the Post Sarbanes-Oxley Era. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 114 (3), 381-392 (2013).
24. Veenstra, EM., Ellemers, N.: ESG Indicators as Organizational Performance Goals: Do Rating Agencies Encourage a Holistic Approach? *Sustainability*. 2020; 12(24):10228. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410228>
25. Swarnodeep, H., Taylan, M., Van Diem, N.: ESG-Linked Compensation, CEO Skills, and Shareholder Welfare, *The Review of Corporate Finance Studies*, Volume 12, Issue 4, November 2023, Pages 939–985, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rcfs/cfad012>.
26. Baraibar-Diez, E., Odriozola M. D., Fernández Sánchez, J. L. : Sustainable compensation policies and its effect on environmental, social, and governance scores. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 2019, 26(6), 1457–1472. 10.1002/csr.1760
27. European Council: Directive (EU) 2022/2381 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 November 2022 on improving the gender balance among directors of listed companies and related measures (Text with EEA relevance) (2022). Internet: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022L2381&qid=1674239108914>, last accessed 2024/04/04.
28. European Council: Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 (2024). Internet: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-6145-2024-INIT/en/pdf>, last accessed 2024/04/05.
29. European Parliament: First green light to new bill on firms' impact on human rights and environment (2024). Internet: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20240318IPR19415/first-green-light-to-new-bill-on-firms-impact-on-human-rights-and-environment>, last accessed 2024/04/05.
30. Eccles, R.G., Johnstone-Louis, M., Mayer, C., Stroehle, J.C.: The Board's Role in Sustainability (2020). *Harvard Business Review* (September-October 2020). Internet: <https://hbr.org/2020/09/the-boards-role-in-sustainability>, last accessed 2024/04/05.

31. Haanaes, K., Cantale, S.: The crucial role of the board in driving sustainable business transformation (2023). IMD Sustainability Toolkit no.4. Internet: <https://www.imd.org/iby-imd/sustainability/the-crucial-role-of-the-board-in-driving-sustainable-business-transformation/>, last accessed 2024/04/05.
32. INSEAD, BCG, Heidrick & Struggles: The Role of the Board in the Sustainability Era (2023). Internet: <https://web-assets.bcg.com/18/fe/f361fe764478a4255fdd2881e21a/the-role-of-the-board-in-the-sustainability-era.pdf>, last accessed 2024/04/05.
33. Competent Boards & Copenhagen Business School: How competent is your board? A ground-breaking tool to measure sustainability credentials (2024). Internet: <https://competentboards.com/app/uploads/2024/01/A-Ground-Breaking-Tool-to-Measure-Sustainability-Credentials-by-Competent-Boards.pdf>, last accessed 2024/04/05.
34. Financial Times (Schumacher, K.): Japan Inc must do more to reduce greenwashing risks (2023). Internet: <https://www.ft.com/content/9c02baa2-447d-4742-beb9-8c83bc3ecc88>, last accessed 2024/04/05.
35. World Business Council for Sustainable Development – WBCSD: Board directors’ duties and ESG considerations in decision-making. Internet: <https://www.wbcsd.org/Programs/Redefining-Value/Business-Decision-Making/Governance-and-Internal-Oversight/Resources/Board-directors-duties-and-ESG-considerations-in-decision-making> (2020), last accessed 2024/02/23.
36. Daum, J., Ciccarelli, K.: Sustainability in the Spotlight: Has ESG lost Momentum in the Boardroom? Harvard Law School Forum on Corporate Governance, 27th July 2023. Internet: Sustainability in the Spotlight: Has ESG Lost Momentum in the Boardroom? (harvard.edu), last accessed, 2024/04/05.
37. Alm, M., Winberg, J.: How Does Gender Diversity on Corporate Boards Affect the Firm Financial Performance? Internet: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/43561419.pdf> (2016), last accessed 2021/03/25.
38. Waterstraat, S., Kustner, C., Koch, M.: Does Board Composition Taking Account of Sustainability Expertise Influence ESG Ratings? An Exploratory Study of European Banks. In Society 5.0: First International Conference, Society 5.0 2021, Virtual Event, June 22–24, 2021, Revised Selected Papers 1 (pp. 129-138). Springer International Publishing.
39. Terjesen, S., Sealy, R., Singh, V.: Women Directors of Corporate Boards: A Review and Research Agenda. *Corporate Governance: An international review*, 17(3), 320-37 (2009).
40. Carter, D.A., Simkins, B.J., Simpson, G.W.: Corporate Governance, Board Diversity and Firm Value. *The Financial Review*, 38, 33-53 (2003).
41. Carter, D.A., D’Souza, F., Simkins, B.J., Simpson, G.W.: The Gender and Ethnic Diversity of US Boards and Board Committees and Firms. *Corporate Governance: An International review* 18(5), 396-414, (2010).
42. Westphal, J.D., Milton, L.P.: How Experience and Network Ties Affect the Influence of Demographic Minorities on Corporate Boards. *Administrative Science Quarterly* 45(2), 366-98 (2000).
43. Konstantin, P., Elena, M.: Relationship between Board Characteristics, ESG and Corporate Performance: A Systematic Review (2022). *Корпоративные финансы*, 16(4), 119-134.
44. Birindelli, G., Dell’Atti, S., Ianuzzi, A.P., Savioli, M.: Composition and Activity of the Board of Directors: Impact on ESG Performance in the Banking System. *Sustainability*, 10(12), 4699 (2018).
45. Garas, S., ElMassah, S.: Corporate governance and corporate social responsibility disclosures: The case of GCC countries. *Critical perspectives on international business*, 14(1), 2-26 (2018).

46. Rao, K., Tilt, C.A., Lester, L.H.: Corporate governance and environmental reporting: an Australian study. *Corporate Governance*, 12(2), 143-163 (2012).
47. Arayssi, M., Dah, M., Jizi, M.: Women on boards, sustainability reporting and firm performance. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 7(3), 376-401 (2016).
48. European Commission: 2019 Report on equality between women and men in the EU. 25 March 2021. Internet: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/aid_development_cooperation_fundamental_rights/annual_report_ge_2019_en.pdf (2019), last accessed 2021/02/21.
49. Arayssi, M., Jizi, M., Tabaja, H.H.: The impact of board composition on the level of ESG disclosures in GCC countries. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 11 (1), 137-161 (2020).
50. Fan, P.S.: Is Board Diversity Important for Firm Performance and Board Independence? – An exploratory study of Singapore Listed Companies. The Monetary Authority of Singapore, MAS Staff Paper No. 52 (2012).
51. Reguera-Alvarado, N., de Fuentes, P., Laffarga, J.: Does Board Gender Diversity Influence Financial Performance? Evidence from Spain. *Journal of Business Ethics* 141, 337–350 (2015).
52. Carter, D.A., D'Souza, F., Simkins, B.J., Simpson, G.W.: The Gender and Ethnic Diversity of US Boards and Board Committees and Firms. *Corporate Governance: An International review* 18(5), 396-414, (2010).
53. Mateos de Cabo, R., Gimeno, R., Nieto, M.J.: Gender Diversity on European Banks' Boards of Directors. *Journal of Business Ethics* 109, 145-62 (2012).
54. Miranda, B., Delgado, C., & Branco, M. C.: Board characteristics, social trust and ESG performance in the European banking sector (2023). *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 16(4), 244.
55. Menicucci, E., & Paolucci, G.: Board diversity and ESG performance: Evidence from the Italian banking sector. *Sustainability*, 14(20), 13447 (2022).
56. Abedin, S. H., Subha, S., Anwar, M., Kabir, M. N., Tahat, Y. A., & Hossain, M.: Environmental performance and corporate governance: evidence from Japan. *Sustainability*, 15(4), 3273 (2023).
57. Nguyen, T. K. G., Ozawa, T., & Fan, P.: Sanpo-yoshi, top management personal values, and ESG performance. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance*, 41, 100903 (2024).
58. Sahar, E., Wan-Hussin, W. N., & Ariffin, M. S. M.: Sustainability performance and board compensation in Japan and ASEAN-5 countries. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 22, S189-S199 (2022).
59. Fernandez-Feijoo, B., Romero, S., Ruiz-Blanco, S.: Women on boards: Do they affect sustainability reporting? *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 21, 351–364 (2014).
60. Tamimi, N., Sebastianelli, R.: Transparency among S&P 500 companies: an analysis of ESG disclosure scores. *Management Decision*, 55(8), 1660-1680 (2017).
61. Carter, D.A., Simkins, B.J., Simpson, G.W.: Corporate Governance, Board Diversity and Firm Value. *The Financial Review*, 38, 33-53 (2003).
62. Helfaya, A., Moussa, T.: Do Board's Corporate Social Responsibility Strategy and Orientation Influence Environmental Sustainability Disclosure? UK Evidence. *Business, Strategy, Environment*, 26, 1061–1077 (2017).
63. Setó-Pamies, D.: The relationship between women directors and corporate social responsibility. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 22, 334–345 (2015).
64. Wooldridge, J.M.: *Introduction to Econometrics*. Hampshire, Cengage (2015).